

THE PROCESS OF FORMATION OF COTTON CLUSTERS IN THE SYSTEM OF THE AGRO-INDUSTRIAL COMPLEX

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Abstract. *This article demonstrates that regional clustering is considered one of the important ways to improve the competitiveness of the national economy in the current context. In the wake of globalization, the agro-industrial complex continues to develop, fostering cooperation and integration, a process that benefits the economy of the Republic of Tajikistan. The article discusses the organizational possibilities, methods, and barriers to cluster formation in the region under study. The author offers several useful suggestions regarding the functional structure of cotton cluster formation in agro-industrial areas and their effectiveness.*

Keywords: *functional structure, agro-industrial complex, cooperation and integration, economic efficiency, agricultural sector development, cluster formation, production, supply, storage, and sales.*

In today's environment, regional clustering is considered one of the important ways to enhance the competitiveness of the national economy. The development of the agro-industrial complex and the formation of cooperation and integration processes continue in the wake of globalization, a process that benefits the economy of the Republic of Tajikistan. This process has played a special role in the formation of agro-industrial clusters, particularly cotton clusters in the regions, and remains applicable from a methodological and stylistic perspective. Cotton clustering in the region does not contradict the goals and objectives of integration and cooperation, but rather, collectively, contributes to the development of entrepreneurship in the agro-industrial system.

Regardless of the process of cotton cluster formation within the agro-industrial complex, it goes through complex and lengthy stages, but all issues in the context of organizing the agricultural production, technological, and innovation chain are being addressed very closely. This is important and will benefit the socioeconomic situation of the country's regions in the near future. However, domestic experience does not provide a unified view on the mechanism, principles, and functions of cotton clusters. The concept of forming cotton clusters in the regions of the Republic of Tajikistan demonstrates that the primary foundation for cotton cluster development is the collective operation of the agro-industrial complex, ensuring the efficient use of natural resources and the competitiveness of domestic goods and products in the country's regions. [8]

Under current conditions in agriculture and other areas of the agro-industrial system, these clusters do not function properly. Analysis and research into the cotton clustering process in the republic's regions demonstrates that attempts to form these clusters on the basis of Soviet-era agro-industrial enterprises without incorporating the experience of economically developed countries and the global economic system, particularly from a scientifically sound perspective, are not yielding the desired results. Hence, the objective need for collective development of the agro-industrial complex based on clustering, including the cotton cluster, which ensures the competitiveness of its participants and the efficient use of economic resources.

Russian and international scholars hold differing views on the theoretical and methodological aspects of developing agro-industrial cotton clusters. Some hold the opinion that "...there are two distinct modes of cotton cluster operation. First, there is the organization of cotton clusters 'from above,' initiated by the state, the government, and national and local authorities, and the organization of cluster participants 'from below.'" Another group of scientists is of the opinion that "...the organization of agro-industrial cotton clusters will yield the desired results when integration begins 'from below', and its participants unite independently to improve the competitiveness of domestic products and resolve issues of cluster formation..." From this point of view, the sectoral organization

of cotton-growing clusters of the agro-industrial system provides broad opportunities for ensuring the efficient use of the region's potential, and its development in modern conditions should naturally accelerate. [6]

According to E. N. Tereshin, "...in the context of the not very good development of the agro-industrial complex and trust between the subjects of the agro-food market, the formation of cotton clusters requires the priority of the role of coordination with government agencies at the local level; greater efficiency in the formation of cotton clusters through state efforts and support achieved "from above" will be brought to..." Or: "...using their capabilities, these clusters can transfer new knowledge, scientific discoveries and inventions, as well as quickly and effectively adapt them to innovations in demand by the market...". This, in turn, requires science and practice to solve a number of new problems for the further development of the agro-industrial complex, especially the agricultural sector. [7]

It is important to note that cotton clusters ensure the integration of economic activity and the competitiveness of regional, international, and local markets, and also consider the study of the methodological aspects, principles, and special functions of their functioning necessary for the development of the country's regions. Therefore, "...the formation and development of the cotton industry as a system of economic relations in the agricultural sector is a complex and lengthy process, and its application to the state of society's material capabilities, the development of production infrastructure, and the cotton market, as well as the existence of special laws for its development, state regulation, and the development of the regional market depends on..." [5]

From a scientific and practical perspective, the formation and development of cotton clusters in the agro-industrial system also requires the mental (psychological) state of its participants, mutual trust, cultural development, and a level of financial literacy. These factors contribute to the centralization of the region's resource and natural resource potential, the development of agro-industrial enterprises and the mutual connections of participants, and the attraction of greater investment in the country's economy.

The cotton cluster plays a central role in the regional economy, facilitating the development of domestic markets and the emergence of new participants in its chain, ensuring price stability and abundance in the region's agri-food market. Incorporating a cluster approach into the development of the agro-industrial complex offers a number of advantages and is crucial for local and regional governments, business development agencies, and participants in these clusters. [9]

Thus, three groups or types of cotton clusters are distinguished based on their functional structure:

- a regional structure with economic dynamism in its sectors, stimulating the attraction of a larger number of scientific institutions (research centers, universities and institutes, etc.);
- a vertically integrated production chain that plays a key role in the production process (supplier, producer, seller, and consumer), i.e., the circulation of goods and products;
- a highly integrated industry (e.g., agro-industrial cotton clusters), which achieves sectoral integration and a very high level of activity.

Over time, cotton clusters will attract more foreign capital, large investments, and efficient production management, increase the number of taxpayers and a special tax base, generate new jobs, create good funds for joint ventures, and lead to further economic restructuring. Agriculture and large companies are central elements of the cotton cluster, maintaining healthy competition between them, which differs significantly from cartels or financial-industrial groups. The system for organizing the competitiveness of enterprises and organizations in the agro-industrial system attracts increasingly more producers, suppliers, and buyers to organize production specialization, cooperation, and integration. [4]

The organization of cotton clusters facilitates a unique form of agro-industrial innovation. New innovative products and the use of modern technologies are also observed, which is aimed at further developing new knowledge and new goods and products for the agro-industrial complex. This is especially true for the food market. It is precisely through the proactive interactions between cotton

cluster participants that they produce and sell effective new innovative developments and high-quality products that meet market demands. Several key factors should be considered, namely, government policy in the country's regions for the formation of cotton clusters and the development of agro-industrial sectors, as well as emergency situations that—for various reasons—may render company management unable to manage their own management, etc. [3]

In general, cotton clusters act as a new organizational and economic entity in the agro-industrial complex, the ultimate goal of which is to ensure the competitiveness of the economy, the region, or its individual sectors. Here, "...the goal of cluster policy is to improve the quality of the region's socio-economic development by creating favorable conditions for the competitiveness of economic entities forming cotton clusters in the region..." Supporting its development in the region by reducing production costs, providing financial support and access to the regional market, facilitating greater investment, and developing market infrastructure are important components of cluster policy in the regions. [2]

Along with political, financial, and economic institutions, ensuring effective macroeconomic policy is also considered an important factor in the formation of agro-industrial cotton clusters in the region, which contributes to the development of regional end products at the microeconomic level. Moreover, "...the effectiveness of clustering at the meso-level in agriculture and the cotton processing industry, achieved through vertical integration, eliminates sectoral and technological-innovation barriers between them..." This also depends on the capabilities of enterprises and organizations in the process of organizing goods and services, stable demand, and the effective use of advanced production, distribution, and consumption methods.

At the same time, cluster policy serves as an important tool for the development of the national and regional economy, local entrepreneurship and the small and medium business environment, company potential, and employee professionalism. Effective production management, development of market infrastructure, and the participation of research institutions and suppliers ensure raw materials and fair competition for cluster participants.

The formation of cotton clusters in regional conditions depends on a number of factors and conditions, the most important of which are: geographic integration and the relationships between cluster participants, the size and share of small and medium businesses, competition between cluster participants in regional markets, and the development of agricultural sectors, among others. Furthermore, "...government bodies play an important role in the implementation of clustering policy and play an important role in enhancing regional and national competitiveness as a priority area of state policy..." Cluster policy is the quality of support for the integration process and the effective functioning of its participants, as well as the quality of initiative and creativity in the activities of agricultural and agro-industrial enterprises. [1]

As experience in regional economic development shows, the most effective economic system is one that ensures fair competition among domestic producers. The competitive effect in these cases is due to "...direct competition between companies and the distribution of profits between them. Competing with each other, ambitions, and the desire to take an active position in their localities allow for a strategy of overcoming each other..." Competition between cotton cluster participants is considered a key element of the clustering concept and distinguishes the cluster from other forms of agro-industrial development, such as cooperation and integration, which contribute to the increased competitiveness of the country's regions as a whole.

Interdependence and competition in cotton clusters operate in several directions. Internal competition within clusters promotes the development and improvement of production efficiency, the motivation of its participants, the improvement and search for new paths to innovative development, territorial and geographic convergence, and also helps ensure fair competition among enterprises and organizations in the agro-industrial complex. Industrial clusters. Production competition in these clusters is a necessary and mandatory condition, helping not only to acquire end consumers but also to attract more resources, political, and public support.

State intervention in regional economic development, traditionally driven by the failure of market mechanisms (in particular, the social and environmental conditions due to the financial and economic crisis), is based on state failures. These and other factors will not influence the formation and further development of cotton clusters in the republic's regions.

Thus, cluster policy represents a mixed form of state economic policy, consisting of the integration of industrial and agricultural policies, regional policies, policies supporting business development, attracting greater domestic and foreign capital, innovation, scientific and technical, and educational policies, and policies for the effective performance of its participants and aimed at the sustainable development of the region. Local government bodies take a special position on the development of clustering, considering state policy mandatory for the formation and development of cotton clusters and also assessing the development of market infrastructure for these clusters as an important factor in the competitiveness of domestic production. These policies also include goods and economic incentives.

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